

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AND SOCIAL SKILLS DEVELOPMENT OF SECOND YEAR BEED STUDENTS: BASIS FOR ACADEMIC SUPPORT

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between parental involvement and the social skills development of 30 second-year BEED students at St. Peter's College during the school year 2023-2024, using a quantitative approach with face-to-face surveys. The survey explored parental involvement in social interaction, learning experiences, and decision-making, alongside students' social skills in educational settings, school success, and peer interactions. Data analysis, employing descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean, Pearson correlation, and ANOVA, revealed that most respondents were female and aged 19-21. Learning experience scored highest for parental involvement, while peer influence ranked highest for social skills development. A significant positive correlation was found between parental involvement and social skills development, particularly in education and peer relationships, with demographic factors like age, gender, parents' occupation, and economic status showing consistent benefits of parental engagement. The study highlights the critical role of active parental involvement in enhancing students' social and academic outcomes, recommending increased parental support and further research to explore these dynamics across diverse populations and longer time frames.

Keywords: *parental involvement, social skills development*

INTRODUCTION

Parental involvement plays a pivotal role in shaping the social development of students. Parental supervision, support, and modelling greatly impact children's

development and refinement of critical social skills as they go through the intricacies of social interactions. Parents are the main influence on their children's social skills from early childhood through adolescence. This introduction delves into the deep relationship that exists between parental participation and the development of social skills. It emphasizes how parents help their children acquire critical skills, including collaboration, empathy, communication, and conflict resolution. We can see the significant influence of family dynamics on the social development of kids and teenagers by appreciating the vital role parents play in promoting social competence.

Parental involvement refers to the active engagement of parents in various aspects of their child's life, including education, extracurricular activities, and social interactions. This involvement can manifest in numerous ways, such as attending school functions, helping with homework, or participating in community activities. Research suggests that children whose parents are actively involved tend to exhibit better social skills, higher academic achievement, and more positive attitudes toward school and learning. Supportive and engaged parents provide children with a sense of security and confidence, fostering an environment conducive to social development.

The development of social skills is a critical aspect of a child's overall growth, significantly influencing their ability to interact effectively with peers, family members, and society at large. Social skills encompass a range of behaviors, including communication, empathy, cooperation, and conflict resolution, all are essential for successful interpersonal relationships. Given the importance of these skills, understanding the factors that contribute to their development is paramount. One such factor is parental involvement, which plays a crucial role in shaping a child's social competencies.

In conclusion, parental involvement's profound impact on the children's social skills development cannot be overstated. From providing supervision and support to serving as role models, parents play a critical role in guiding their children through the complexities of social interactions. The strong relationship between parental engagement and acquiring essential social skills such as empathy, communication, cooperation, and conflict resolution underscores the importance of active and sustained parental participation. By recognizing and promoting the significant role of parents in fostering social competence, we can better support the holistic development of children and adolescents. Ultimately, the involvement of parents is a cornerstone in nurturing well-rounded, socially adept individuals who are equipped to navigate the challenges of interpersonal relationships throughout their lives.

Related Literature

Parental Involvement

According to Bryan (2020), children are likely to excel academically when their parents' actively participate in their education. Education is necessary and important to society. Education provides insight and increases knowledge and skill. It is important to developing human capital and an individual's ability to provide a better living. Thus, the

education of parents, as well as their economic status, is a crucial element in educational outcomes of students.

EI Nokali et al. (2021) assert this literature review on parental involvement as those behaviors shown by the parents, both in home and school settings, meant to support the development of their children's social/emotional skills and facilitate their educational success. Socio-emotional intelligence has been discussed as comprising skills that facilitate the processing of social and emotional information and improve problem-solving and leadership-context activities. The child must interact with other people and consequently deal with varied emotions in social situations.

Social Interaction

Muigai et al. (2019) discusses the importance of parental involvement in education, including its impact on social development. It covers various aspects of parental involvement, including communication, volunteering, and support at home. It emphasizes that parental involvement goes beyond simply attending school events or helping with homework; it encompasses various activities and behaviors that contribute to children's success in school and life. When parents engage in their children's education, they provide valuable support, guidance, and encouragement that fosters social skills, self-confidence, and interpersonal relationships. Through positive parent-child interactions and modeling of pro-social behaviors, parents contribute to developing empathy, communication skills, and conflict resolution abilities in their children.

Learning Experience

Epstein et al. (2019) the book delves into various dimensions of parental involvement, emphasizing the importance of parents' active participation in their children's educational journey and the quality and nature of this involvement. He argues that parental involvement goes beyond mere attendance at school events or parent-teacher conferences; it encompasses a range of supportive actions and behaviors that foster a collaborative relationship between parents and educators. It demonstrates how fostering school, family, and community partnerships can lead to students positive outcomes. These outcomes extend beyond academic achievement to encompass holistic development, including improved social-emotional skills, enhanced self-efficacy, and a stronger sense of belonging within the school community.

According to Hattie et al. and Timperley et al. (2020), this comprehensive review explores the effectiveness of feedback in improving student learning outcomes. While not specific to parental feedback, it highlights the importance of timely, specific, and actionable feedback from various sources, including parents, in enhancing student performance and motivation. This review underscores the importance of feedback as a continuous process within a supportive and collaborative learning environment. When parents engage in ongoing dialogue with their children about their academic progress, they create opportunities for meaningful feedback exchanges that foster learning, growth, and motivation.

Decision-making

In Epstein's et al. (2021) model, involvement between families and schools is described within six areas: parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making, and community collaboration. Our use of the term parental involvement in this article draws from three of these areas (communicating, learning at home, and decision-making), those most prevalent in the literature in relation to the engagement of parents in the school curriculum. Epstein describes communicating as information about the learner and what is happening in the school, moving in both directions between home and school; two-way communication is particularly important for meaningful, effective partnerships. Learning at home is described as teachers and schools assisting parents to help their children with schoolwork and other school-curriculum related activities. The decision-making descriptor is used to encompass ways in which parents have representation and input into school and school curriculum decisions.

Social Skills Development

Hindman et al. and Morrison et al. (2019) identified parenting practices as important for social skills, even among young children. Greater nurturing and a supportive approach toward independence and integration have been shown to help children develop strong self-regulation and interactive skills. Positive parenting contributes to successful social adaptation by providing the child with guidance in social expectations and behavior management, and showing affection and encouragement in everyday situations. Positive parenting can even buffer the effects of negative child factors (e.g., difficult temperament) on the development of self-regulation, while negative and/or authoritarian parenting styles increase the risk of poor social behavior.

Educational Environment

Thapa et al. (2019) review provides a comprehensive examination of research on school climate and its multifaceted impact on student outcomes, particularly academic achievement. The review underscores the critical importance of cultivating a positive school climate, characterized by supportive relationships, clear expectations, and a safe and welcoming environment, in fostering academic success. A safe and welcoming school environment is fundamental to promoting students' academic achievement. When students feel physically and emotionally safe at school, they are more likely to engage in learning activities, participate actively in class discussions, and take academic risks. Moreover, a welcoming environment that celebrates diversity and inclusivity fosters a sense of belonging among all students, regardless of their backgrounds or identities, promoting equitable access to educational opportunities and enhancing academic outcomes.

According to Abrami et al. (2021), meta-analysis provides valuable insights into instructional strategies to foster students' critical thinking skills. By synthesizing findings from various studies, the meta-analysis identifies effective approaches that promote critical thinking and problem-solving abilities across diverse educational settings. Effective instructional strategies for promoting critical thinking enhance students'

performance in specific subject areas and equip them with transferable skills that are applicable in diverse academic and real-world settings. By cultivating critical inquiry and problem-solving culture, educators prepare students to navigate complex challenges, make informed decisions, and contribute meaningfully to society.

School Success

Epstein et al. (2019) developed a model of family-school involvement that includes dimensions such as parenting, communicating, and learning at home. The model suggests that effective communication between parents and schools, and supportive home learning environments can bolster children's social skills. These enhanced social skills are associated with better academic performance, enabling children to navigate school environments more effectively.

Peer Influence

According to Boivin et al. (2020), peer relationships are thought to play an important role in children's development. They offer unique opportunities for getting acquainted with the social norms and processes involved in interpersonal relationships and learning new social skills. They also provide contexts in which capacities for self-control may be tested and refined. Childhood peer relations are also multifaceted: children experience peer interactions through their participation in group activities as well as through their dyadic (i.e., one-on-one) associations with friends. These different facets of peer experiences are seen as providing age-related developmental opportunities for the construction of the self, with peer group experiences progressively gaining in importance and culminating in middle childhood before giving way to friendships as the most central feature in late childhood and adolescence.

Related Studies

Kerr and Stattin (2020) investigated the relationship between parental knowledge, parent-child communication, and various aspects of adolescent adjustment. One key finding of the study is the importance of open and supportive communication between parents and adolescents in facilitating discussions about potential decisions. When adolescents feel comfortable discussing their thoughts, concerns, and decisions with their parents, it can lead to positive outcomes in multiple domains of adolescent development. Specifically, when parents and adolescents engage in open communication, they are more likely to involve adolescents in decision-making. This collaborative approach allows adolescents to express their opinions, preferences, and concerns, leading to decisions more reflective of their needs and values.

Moreover, Soenens et al. (2019) delved into the intricate dynamics of parenting styles and their impact on adolescent development, particularly focusing on the role of supportive parenting in fostering autonomy and positive functioning. The study emphasizes the significance of open communication and discussions between parents and adolescents in creating autonomy-supportive parenting contexts. In these contexts, adolescents feel empowered to weigh the pros and cons of different choices. Through

open communication and discussions about choices, autonomy-supportive parents help adolescents develop decision-making competence. Adolescents learn to consider various perspectives, weigh the consequences of their actions, and make informed decisions that align with their values and goals. This decision-making process promotes adolescents' sense of agency and responsibility, preparing them for the challenges of adulthood.

Additionally, Castillo et al. (2020) demonstrated that students do better academically, attend school more regularly, and score higher on standardized tests when their parents are also invested in their education. Parents can support their children's learning in a variety of ways, including by assisting with homework, attending school events, being active in school decision-making, and maintaining open lines of communication with instructors.

In a related study, Arriero (2020) found that two main issues arise from the amount of parental involvement in children's learning at home: the type of communication parents sustain with their children and the general influence of the home environment. This implies that communication with parents ranges from positive or praising to negative disciplining for learning purposes.

Moreover, parental involvement's quality matters just as much as quantity. For example, Fan and Chen (2020) emphasized the significance of responsive parenting, wherein parents actively engage in reciprocal interactions with their children, fostering emotional regulation and social understanding. Similarly, Miller and colleagues (2018) underscored the importance of parental modeling in social skills development, showing how children often mimic the social behaviors they observe in their parents.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the level of parental involvement and social skills development of second-year BEED students in St. Peter's College during the School Year 2023 – 2024. The result of the study would be the basis for academic support.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How are the respondents distributed in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. parents' occupation; and
 - 1.4. economic status
2. What is the level of parental involvement as perceived by the respondents with respect to:
 - 2.1. social interaction;
 - 2.2. learning experiences; and
 - 2.3. decision-making
3. How do the respondents assess the 2nd year BEED social skills development in terms of:
 - 3.1. educational environment;
 - 3.2. school success; and

- 3.3. peer influence
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of 2nd year BEED parental involvement and their social skills development in terms of:
 - 4.1. educational environment;
 - 4.2. school success; and
 - 4.3. peer influence
5. Is there a significant difference in the respondents' level of assessment of the 2nd year BEED parental involvement and their social skills development when grouped according to age, gender, parents' occupation, and economic status?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan on parental involvement can be designed?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive correlation method of research. This method is a research approach used to identify relationships between variables without necessarily causation. In this method, researchers observe and describe how variables are naturally related in the real world. It involves collecting data on multiple variables of interest and analyzing the patterns of correlations between them. As defined by Fluet (2020), descriptive research is a quantitative research method employed to characterize traits or functions and assess specific hypotheses. Fluet further emphasized the need for precision and clarity when defining the research problem for this type of study.

Questionnaires and in-depth interviews were employed to collect data for this data. This approach aligns with the conclusive quantitative research technique, which aimed to test specific hypotheses and elucidate properties or functions, as Vieira et al. (2020) outlined.

This approach is expected to yield accurately and precisely represent the situation. The study involved collecting, organizing, and analyzing data to derive meaningful insights from the findings. Key variables to be examined include the attributes of teacher respondents, their research competence, and their level of research engagement.

Research Site

The study was conducted at St. Peter's College, Iligan City. Situated in barangay Sabayle, Saray, Iligan City. St. Peter College is a private, non-stock, non-sectaria, institution comprising different colleges, namely the College of Education, Criminology, Engineering, Arts and Sciences, Computer Studies, and Business Administration. The school had separate buildings for various colleges, a library, a canteen for everyone. The school had lecture rooms and provided audio-visual presentation equipment for classroom discussions. The school also had various facilities for different subjects, such as a chemistry laboratory, drawing and engineering rooms, a criminology laboratory, a martial arts room, a computer room, a speech laboratory, and an AVR (Audio-Visual Room).

The research in this setting was timely, aligning with the academic calendar for the school year 2023-2024. This ensures that the findings are relevant and actionable, serving as the basis for academic support from parental involvement and the social skills development of 2nd-year BEED students.

St. Peter's College fosters collaboration between researchers and students, making it an ideal environment to explore and improve parental involvement and social skills development. The study took place within the campus facilities and classrooms. The study setting in St. Peter College, Iligan City, provides a dynamic backdrop for investigating the parental involvement and social skills development of 2nd-year BEED students.

Respondents/Sample and Sampling Method

This study examined parental involvement and social skills development among second-year BEED students at St. Peter's College in the school year 2023-2024 with a diverse and representative population of students.

The study included 30 respondents in the study. This group comprises students from specific academic programs within the College of Education at St. Peter's College. The respondents were selected from the second-year Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) students, which was the primary area of interest for investigating parental involvement and social skills development.

Data Gathering Method Instruments and Process

A letter signed by the researchers asking permission to launch the questionnaire in St. Peter's College will be sent to the Dean of the College of Education for approval. This letter of request to conduct a survey select 2nd Bachelor in Elementary Education (BEED) students as respondents for the research. Once approval is obtained, the researcher will coordinate with the College of Education to schedule a time for administering the survey.

The research questionnaire was designed to gather valuable insights into parental involvement and social skills development at St. Peter's College. The questionnaire is divided into three parts:

The first part of the questionnaire dealt with the respondent's profile in terms of age, gender, parents' occupation and economic status.

The second part of the questionnaire is adopted-- a questionnaire that underwent validation for testing and retesting to thirty (30) BEED students. The questionnaire assessed on parental involvement based on the functions of involvement. Students assessed the parental involvement using the following scale: *at all times*, *most of the times*, *sometimes*, and *never*. The subsections in this part may include social interaction, learning experience and decision-making.

Source: <https://www.google.com/maps>

Figure 2. Map of the St. Peter's College

The third part of the questionnaire is adapted questionnaire to assess social skills development. Students will assess their learning engagement using the following scale: highly observable, observable, somewhat observable, and not observable. The subsections in this part may include areas such as educational environment, school success, and peer influence.

Data Analysis Method

The following tools were utilized in the data analysis to systematically process, interpret, and analyze the data collection and effectively address the research objectives and questions.

For Research Question No. 1, the respondents' demographic profile used frequency and percentage of age and gender. In research, the presentation and interpretation of data rely heavily on frequency and percentage. They make it easy for the researchers to understand the data clearly.

For Research Question No. 2 and 3, the statistical mean was used to analyze the students' perceptions of tactics that improve the parental involvement and social skills development. The mean condenses a large amount of data into a single value, making it easier to grasp and communicate the overall the characteristic of the data set.

For Research Question No. 4, Pearson r was utilized to determine whether there is a significant relationship between the parental involvement and social skills development. It helps researchers to test the hypotheses correlation in the population from which the sample was drawn.

For Research Question No. 5, ANOVA or Analysis of variance, was used to compare the significant differences between the independent and variables.

For Research Question No.6, a comprehensive action plan was designed to determine the key areas of the lowest mean and the significant relationship between the variables.

Research Ethics

It was crucial to ensure the privacy and anonymity of the students who participated in the research. Students may be inclined to participate honestly and openly if they were assured that their identities and personal information had been kept confidential. The following ethical concerns were to be undertaken:

First was informed consent, obtaining information consent from all participating students and clearly explaining the purpose of the study, the data collection process, and how their information had been used. This was to ensure that they had the option to withdraw from the study at any time without consequences.

Second was Data De-identification, students were asked to remove or replace any personally identifiable information (such as names, school names, or contact details) from the data during analysis. Pseudonym assignments may be done to participants to protect their identities.

Third was Secure Data Storage, which safeguarded the collected data by storing it securely, using encryption where necessary, and limiting access to authorized personnel only. This ensured that data was not accidentally disclosed to unauthorized parties.

Finally, for the last ethical review, ethical approval was sought from an institutional review board (IRB) or ethics committee to ensure that the researched design and data handling procedures meet ethical standards.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study focused on the parental involvement and social skills development of second-year BEED students at St. Peter’s College, during the school year 2023– 2024. It was limited to these students.

Its variables were age, gender, parents’ occupation, and economic status. In contrast, the independent variables dealt with parental involvement, namely social interaction, learning experiences, and decision-making. The dependent variable was limited to social skills development categorized as educational environment, school success, and peer influence.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. How are the respondents distributed in terms of:

- 1.1. age;
- 1.2. gender;
- 1.3. parents’ occupation; and
- 1.4. economic status

Table 1: *Distribution of Respondents’ Profile in terms of Age*

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
19-21	21	70.00
22-24	8	26.67
25 and above	1	3.33
Overall	30	100.00

Table 1 presents the distribution of the respondents according to age. The data revealed that **21 (70%)** belonged to the **19 to 21-years-old** category, which obtained the highest frequency. This implies a dominance of 19 to 21-years-old engaged in second year BEED students within the institution. The concentration of 19 to 21-year-old suggests that the perspectives, preferences, and behaviors of this age group are likely to influence the overall findings of the survey heavily. As future educators, these students are likely to recognize the importance of parental involvement in education. Their perspectives on the level and nature of parental support they received during their schooling years can offer valuable insights into how parental involvement contributes to developing social skills, academic achievement, and overall well-being.

On the other hand, data revealed that out of 30 respondents' **1 (3.33%)** of respondents were **25 years old and above**, which obtained the lowest frequency. This indicates that the students in this age group are relatively underrepresented within the second-year BEED cohort. The low frequency of respondents aged 25 and above suggests a potential age distribution imbalance within the student population. It is possible that individuals aged 25 and above represent a minority of second-year BEED students due to delayed entry into higher education. These students may have taken non-traditional pathways, such as working or raising a family, before pursuing their degree.

National Center for Education Statistics (2021) provides data and analysis on various aspects of education in the United States, including demographic trends such as age distribution among students. The report offers insights into age-related patterns in enrollment, achievement, and educational attainment, informing policy decisions and initiatives to address the needs of students at different stages of development. It explores academic achievement disparities among students of different ages, considering factors such as developmental readiness, learning trajectories, and educational experiences. The report examines age-related variations in standardized test scores, academic performance indicators, and achievement gaps across demographic groups, shedding light on the complex interplay between age, academic achievement, and socio-demographic factors.

Table 2. *Distribution of Respondents' Profile in terms of Gender*

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Male	6	20.00
Female	24	80.00
Overall	30	100.00

Table 2 presents the distribution of the respondents according to gender. The data revealed that **24 (80%)** belonged to the **female**, which obtained the highest frequency. This indicates that many second-year BEED students are female, reflecting a significant gender disparity within the cohort. The high frequency of female respondents suggests

that the BEED program may attract a predominantly female student population. The data might suggest that females have a stronger inclination towards pursuing careers in elementary education than males. Understanding these preferences can provide valuable insights for educational institutions in tailoring their programs and support systems to cater to the needs and interests of their student demographic.

On the other hand, data revealed that out of 30 respondents, **6 (20%)** of the respondents were **male**, which obtained the lowest frequency. The data underscores a significant gender disparity within the respondent pool, with male respondents representing only 20%. This indicates that males are a minority group within the context of the BEED program, potentially facing unique challenges or experiences compared to their female counterparts. The lower representation of male respondents could be attributed to societal norms and expectations surrounding gender roles and career choices. Traditionally, teaching, especially at the elementary level, has been associated with femininity, which may discourage some males from pursuing careers in education.

According to Gurian et al. (2021), the book explores how boys and girls may exhibit distinct learning, influenced by biological, cognitive, and socio-cultural factors. It discusses research findings suggesting that boys and girls may process information differently, have varying attention spans, and respond differently to instructional approaches. By recognizing these differences, educators and parents can better tailor teaching strategies to meet the diverse learning needs of boys and girls. The book provides valuable insights into gender-based differences in learning. It offers practical guidance for educators and parents seeking to support the diverse needs of boys and girls in educational settings. By understanding and addressing these differences, educators can create more inclusive, equitable, and effective learning environments that foster the success of all students, regardless of gender.

Table 3. Distribution of Respondents' Profile in terms of Parents' Occupation

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Self-employed	19	63.33
Employed (Government, Public)	11	36.67
Overall	30	100.00

Table 3 presents the distribution of the respondents according to parents' occupation. The data revealed that **19 (63.33%)** belonged to the **self-employed**, which obtained the highest frequency. The high frequency of respondents with self-employed parents suggests a significant presence of entrepreneurial backgrounds within the respondent pool. This indicates that most students may come from families involved in business ventures or self-owned enterprises. The prominence of self-employed parents may also imply a certain level of economic stability within the respondents' families. Entrepreneurial endeavors often involve risks, but successful ventures can lead to

financial security and autonomy. This stability may provide students with a conducive environment for pursuing higher education and career aspirations.

On the other hand, data revealed that **11 (36.67%)** of the 30 respondents had **employed** parents, which obtained the lowest frequency. The presence of employed parents within the survey population may reflect a commitment to stable employment and financial security. These parents may value the stability, benefits, and career advancement opportunities offered by formal employment arrangements, which can significantly impact the household's economic well-being and the upbringing of their children. While the frequency of employed parents may be lower than self-employed parents in this survey population, it's essential to recognize the diversity of occupations and industries represented in this group. Employed parents may work in various sectors, ranging from traditional corporate roles to public service, healthcare, education, and beyond.

According to Lareau (2019), the study provides rich insights into the dynamics of family life, highlighting how parental occupation and socioeconomic status shape parenting practices, family routines, and interactions within the household. By immersing herself in the daily lives of families from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds, she uncovers how parental occupations influence family dynamics and children's experiences. By exploring the linkages between parental occupation, parenting practices, and children's educational experiences, she demonstrates how these factors contribute to disparities in children's academic achievement and social mobility. She illustrates how children from more advantaged socioeconomic backgrounds, characterized by parents with higher occupational status, tend to have access to greater educational opportunities and resources, which can shape their long-term educational outcomes.

Table 4. *Distribution of Respondents' Profile in terms of Economic Status*

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
High	2	6.67
Average	27	90.00
Low	1	3.33
Overall	30	100.00

Table 4 presents the distribution of the respondents according to economic status. The data revealed that **27 (90%)** of the respondents' economic status belonged to the **average**, which obtained the highest frequency. It suggests that this economic bracket is significant in the community or population being studied. This widespread representation indicates that understanding the dynamics within this economic group is crucial for comprehending broader societal trends related to parental involvement and social skills development. The dominance of the average economic status category implies that

middle-class norms and values may heavily influence parental involvement and social skills development within the community. Middle-class families often prioritize education, achievement, and socialization, which can shape parenting styles and approaches to fostering social skills in children.

On the other hand, the data revealed that **1(3.33%)** of the respondents' economic status belonged to the **low**, which obtained the lowest frequency. Families with low economic status often face financial constraints that hinder their ability to actively engage in their children's education and social development. This could mean fewer resources for educational materials, extracurricular activities, or even time constraints due to multiple jobs or unstable work schedules. As a result, these children might receive less guidance, support, and involvement from their parents than their peers from average economic backgrounds.

According to Sirin (2019), a meta-analytic review investigates the relationship between socioeconomic status (SES) and academic achievement. The study synthesizes findings from a wide range of research studies to examine how economic status, as measured by factors parental income, education level, and occupation, impacts students' academic performance. By analyzing the distribution of respondents' characteristics in terms of economic status, the study provides insights into the disparities in educational outcomes associated with socioeconomic factors. Understanding the relationship between SES and academic achievement can inform efforts to address educational inequalities and promote equity in schools and communities.

Research Question 2. What is the level of parental involvement as perceived by the respondents with respect to:

- 2.1. social interaction;**
- 2.2. learning experiences; and**
- 2.3. decision-making**

Table 5. *Distribution of Respondents' Level on Parental Involvement with respect to Social Interaction*

Indicators	Mea n	Description
As a student, I feel supported by my parents in my social interactions.	3.10	Most of the time
As a student, I prefer receiving guidance from my parents on how to navigate social situations.	2.80	Most of the time
As a student, I seek my parents' approval before making social decisions.	3.03	Most of the time
As a student, I believe parental involvement has positively impacted my social development.	3.23	Most of the time

As a student, I prefer discussing my social goals and aspirations with my parents.	2.87	Most of the time
Overall	3.01	Most of the time
Legend: 3.26-4.00 At all Times / Very Positive	1.76-2.50	Sometimes/Negative
2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/ Positive	1.00-1.75	Never/ Very Negative

Table 5 determines the distribution of respondents' level of parental involvement with respect to social interaction. The data exposed the overall mean of **3.0**, described as **most of the time** and interpreted as **positive**. The positive interpretation suggest a generally favorable perception among respondents regarding parental involvement in the context of social interaction. The mean score falls within the range of moderate perception, the fact that it is slightly above the midpoint of the scale suggests an overall positive trend. This indicates that, on the whole, respondents tend to view parental involvement in social interaction as a beneficial factor in their lives. The interpretation of the mean score as positive validates the importance of parental involvement in shaping social interactions during the developmental stage of the respondents. It highlights the significant role that parents play in facilitating and nurturing social skills and interactions among their children.

In line with this, the indicator, **as a student, I believe parental involvement has positively impacted my social development**, got the highest mean of **3.32**, described as **most of the time** and interpreted as **positive**. The high mean score of 3.32 suggests that the majority of respondents believe parental involvement has positively impacted their social development. This indicates a strong perception among students that their parents play a significant and beneficial role in fostering their social skills and interactions. It underscores the influential role that parents play in shaping their children's social behaviors, relationships, and overall development.

Jecinta Muigai (2019) discusses the importance of parental involvement in education, including its impact on social development. It covers various aspects of parental involvement, including communication, volunteering, and support at home. It emphasizes that parental involvement goes beyond simply attending school events or helping with homework; it encompasses a wide range of activities and behaviors that contribute to children's success in school and life. When parents are actively engaged in their children's education, they provide valuable support, guidance, and encouragement that fosters social skills, self-confidence, and interpersonal relationships. Through positive parent-child interactions and modeling of pro social behaviors, parents contribute to the development of empathy, communication skills, and conflict resolution abilities in their children.

On the other hand, the indicator, **as a student, I prefer receiving guidance from my parents on how to navigate social situations**, got the lowest mean of **2.80**, described as **most of the time** and interpreted as **positive**. The low mean score indicates that students may prefer to navigate social situations independently or seek guidance from sources other than their parents. This suggests a desire among students for autonomy and self-reliance in managing their social interactions. The indicator may offer insights into the quality of the parent-child relationship and the level of trust and

communication between students and their parents. A low preference for parental guidance on social situations could indicate a need for parents to foster a more supportive and communicative relationship with their children.

According to Garcia et al. (2020), this meta-analytic review provides a comprehensive synthesis of research findings on the relationship between parental guidance and adolescent social adjustment. They highlight the critical role of parental guidance, involvement, monitoring, and support in promoting adolescent social adjustment and well-being. Interventions and programs aimed at enhancing parental skills and promoting positive parent-child relationships can benefit adolescents' social development and contribute to positive outcomes in various domains of life.

Table 6. *Distribution of Respondents' Level on Parental Involvement with respect to Learning Experience*

Indicators	Mean	Description
As a student, I believe parental involvement positively impacts my learning experiences.	3.33	At all times
As a student, I feel motivated to learn when my parents show interest in my education.	3.60	At all times
As a student, I feel comfortable discussing my academic challenges with my parents.	2.97	Most of the time
As a student, I believe my parents provide valuable insights that enhance my learning.	2.90	Most of the time
As a student, I prefer receiving feedback on my academic performance from my parents.	2.70	Most of the time
Overall	3.10	Most of the time
Legend: 3.26-4.00 At all Times / Very Positive	1.76-2.50	Sometimes/Negative
2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/Positive	1.00-1.75	Never/ Very Negative

Table 6 explains the distribution of respondents' level of parental involvement with respect to learning experience. The data exposed that the overall mean of **3.10**, described as **most of the time** and interpreted as **positive**. The mean score above 3.0 indicates that respondents perceive a high level of parental involvement in their learning experiences. This suggests that parents are actively engaged in various aspects of their children's education, including academic support, communication with teachers, and involvement in school activities.

In line with this, the indicator, **as a student, I feel motivated to learn when my parents show interest in my education**, got the highest mean of **3.60**, described as **at all times** and interpreted as **very positive**. A high mean score implies that student's feel supported and valued when their parents show interest in their education. This supportive environment can foster a positive attitude towards learning, increase engagement in academic activities, and promote a sense of ownership over one's educational journey.

According to Epstein (2019), the book delves into various dimensions of parental involvement, emphasizing not only the importance of parents' active participation in their children's educational journey but also the quality and nature of this involvement. He argues that parental involvement goes beyond mere attendance at school events or parent-teacher conferences; it encompasses a range of supportive actions and behaviors that foster a collaborative relationship between parents and educators. It demonstrates how fostering school, family, and community partnerships can lead to positive outcomes for students. These outcomes extend beyond academic achievement to encompass holistic development, including improved social-emotional skills, enhanced self-efficacy, and a stronger sense of belonging within the school community.

On the other hand, the indicator, **as a student, I prefer receiving feedback on my academic performance from my parents**, got the lowest mean of **2.70**, described as **most of the time** and interpreted as **positive**. This suggests that students may prefer to receive feedback on their academic performance from sources other than their parents. This could indicate a desire for independence and autonomy in managing their academic responsibilities and receiving feedback on their progress. Students may place greater value on feedback from peers or teachers, viewing it as more objective or constructive than feedback from parents, who may be perceived as having a personal or emotional investment in their success.

According to Hattie and Timperley (2020), this comprehensive review explores the effectiveness of feedback in improving student learning outcomes. While not specific to parental feedback, it highlights the importance of timely, specific, and actionable feedback from various sources, including parents, in enhancing student performance and motivation. This review underscores the importance of feedback as a continuous process that occurs within a supportive and collaborative learning environment. When parents engage in ongoing dialogue with their children about their academic progress, they create opportunities for meaningful feedback exchanges that foster learning, growth, and motivation.

Table 7. Distribution of Respondents' Level on Parental Involvement with respect to Decision-making

Indicators	Mean	Description
As a student, I feel comfortable discussing potential decisions with my parents.	2.97	Most of the time
As a student, I prefer considering my parents' perspectives before finalizing a decision.	2.93	Most of the time
As a student, I feel supported by my parents regardless of the decisions I make.	2.93	Most of the time
As a student, I prefer having discussions with my parents to weigh the pros and cons of different choices.	2.73	Most of the time

As a student, I prefer having open and honest communication with my parents about my decision-making process.	2.74	Most of the time
Overall	2.87	Most of the time
Legend:	3.26-4.00 At all Times / Very Positive	1.76-2.50 Sometimes/ Negative
	2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/ Positive	1.00-1.75 Never/ Very Negative

Table 7 explains the distribution of respondents' level of parental involvement with respect to decision-making. The data exposed that the overall mean of **2.87**, described as **most of the time** and interpreted as **positive**. This suggests that respondents perceive a moderate level of parental involvement in decision-making processes. This indicates that parents are somewhat involved in the decisions that affect their children's lives, but there is variability in the extent of their participation. This implies that students may have some degree of autonomy and independence in decision-making, particularly in areas such as academics, extracurricular activities, and social interactions. This reflects the transition from childhood to adolescence, where individuals begin to assert their independence while still seeking guidance from parents.

In line with this, the indicator, as a student, I feel comfortable discussing potential decisions with my parents, got the highest mean of 2.97, described as most of the time and interpreted as positive. It implies that parents are actively involved in decision-making processes, providing guidance, insight, and support to their children. This involvement promotes a collaborative approach to decision-making, where parents and students work together to consider various options and make informed choices. It suggests that students feel comfortable discussing potential decisions with their parents, indicating that there are open lines of communication within the family. This openness fosters an environment where students feel supported and valued, enabling constructive discussions about important decisions.

According to Kerr & Stattin (2020), the study investigates the relationship between parental knowledge, parent-child communication, and various aspects of adolescent adjustment. One key finding of the study is the importance of open and supportive communication between parents and adolescents in facilitating discussions about potential decisions. When adolescents feel comfortable discussing their thoughts, concerns, and decisions with their parents, it can lead to positive outcomes in multiple domains of adolescent development. When parents and adolescents engage in open communication, they are more likely to involve adolescents in decision-making processes. This collaborative approach allows adolescents to express their opinions, preferences, and concerns, leading to decisions that are more reflective of their needs and values.

On the other hand, the indicator, **as a student, I prefer having discussions with my parents to weigh the pros and cons of different choices**, with the lowest mean of **2.73**, described as **most of the time** and interpreted as **positive**. This suggests that students may prefer to make decisions independently or with limited input from their parents. This could indicate a desire for autonomy and self-reliance in decision-making processes. This indicates that students may not prioritize discussions with their parents

when weighing the pros and cons of different choices. This could be due to factors such as communication barriers, lack of trust, or differing perspectives on decision-making.

According to Soenens et al. (2019), the study delves into the intricate dynamics of parenting styles and their impact on adolescent development, particularly focusing on the role of supportive parenting in fostering autonomy and positive functioning. The study emphasizes the significance of open communication and discussions between parents and adolescents in creating autonomy-supportive parenting contexts, where adolescents feel empowered to weigh the pros and cons of different choices. Through open communication and discussions about choices, autonomy-supportive parents help adolescents develop decision-making competence. Adolescents learn to consider various perspectives, weigh the consequences of their actions, and make informed decisions that align with their values and goals. This process of decision-making promotes adolescents' sense of agency and responsibility, preparing them for the challenges of adulthood.

Research Question 3. How do the respondents assess the 2nd year BEED social skills development in terms of:

- 3.1. educational environment;**
- 3.2. school success; and**
- 3.3. peer influence**

Table 8. Distribution of Respondents' Social Skills Development in terms of Educational Environment

Indicators	Mean	Description
As a student, I prefer studying in an environment with ample resources such as books, technology, and materials are available.	3.30	Highly Observable
As a student, I feel that the educational environment effectively prepares students for future academic or professional endeavors.	3.32	Highly Observable
As a student, I believe that a positive educational environment enhances academic achievement.	3.53	Highly Observable
As a student, I feel that the educational environment encourages creativity and innovation in learning.	3.37	Highly Observable
As a student, I find that the educational environment encourages critical thinking and problem-solving skills.	3.20	Observable
Overall	3.34	Highly Observable

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Highly Observable/Very High
1.76-2.50 Somewhat Observable/Low

Table 8 explains the distribution of respondents' social skills development in terms of educational environment with the overall mean of **3.34**, described as **highly observable** and interpreted as **very high**. This means that the overall mean of 3.34 suggests that the respondents' social skills development is highly observable within the educational environment. This indicates that social interactions and behaviors are readily noticeable and likely play a significant role in the learning environment. These insights can provide how various factors within educational environments contribute to the development of social skills. This understanding can inform educators, policymakers, and parents about the effectiveness of different educational approaches in nurturing students' social competencies.

In line with this, the indicator, **as a student, I believe that a positive educational environment enhances academic achievement**, got the highest mean of **3.53**, described as **highly observable** and interpreted as **very high**. This suggests that their perceptions align with research findings indicating the importance of supportive, nurturing, and conducive learning environments. This insight reinforces the significance of considering students' perspectives in educational policymaking and practice.

According to Thapa et al. (2019), the review provides a comprehensive examination of research on school climate and its multifaceted impact on student outcomes, particularly academic achievement. The review underscores the critical importance of cultivating a positive school climate, characterized by supportive relationships, clear expectations, and a safe and welcoming environment, in fostering academic success. A safe and welcoming school environment is fundamental to promoting students' academic achievement. When students feel physically and emotionally safe at school, they are more likely to engage in learning activities, participate actively in class discussions, and take academic risks. Moreover, a welcoming environment that celebrates diversity and inclusivity fosters a sense of belonging among all students, regardless of their backgrounds or identities, thereby promoting equitable access to educational opportunities and enhancing academic outcomes.

On the other hand, the indicator, **as a student, I find that the educational environment encourages critical thinking and problem-solving skills**, got the lowest mean of **3.20**, described as **observable** and interpreted as **high**. The lower mean score indicates a potential mismatch between students' perceptions of the educational environment and the actual development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills. While students may believe that the environment encourages these skills, the data suggest that there may be room for improvement in translating this encouragement into tangible skill development.

According to Abrami et al. (2021), meta-analysis provides valuable insights into instructional strategies aimed at fostering critical thinking skills among students. By synthesizing findings from various studies, the meta-analysis identifies effective approaches that promote critical thinking and problem-solving abilities across diverse

educational settings. Effective instructional strategies for promoting critical thinking not only enhance students' performance in specific subject areas but also equip them with transferable skills that are applicable in diverse academic and real-world settings. By cultivating a culture of critical inquiry and problem-solving, educators prepare students to navigate complex challenges, make informed decisions, and contribute meaningfully to society.

Table 9. *Distribution of Respondents' Social Skills Development in terms of School Success*

Indicators	Mean	Description
As a student, I help resolve conflicts among classmates in a positive and respectful manner.	3.33	Highly Observable
As a student, I respect the opinions and perspectives of others, even if they differ from my own.	3.57	Highly Observable
As a student, I am able to adapt to different social situations and environments within the school community.	3.13	Observable
As a student, I effectively communicate my ideas and thoughts during class discussions.	3.47	Highly Observable
As a student, I actively participate in group discussions and activities in class.	3.33	Highly Observable
Overall	3.37	Highly Observable

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Highly Observable/Very High 1.76-2.50 Somewhat Observable/Low

2.51-3.25 Observable/High 1.00-1.75 Not Observable/Very Low

Table 9 explains the distribution of respondents' social skills development in terms of school success with the overall mean of **3.34**, described as **highly observable** and interpreted as **very high**. This means that the overall mean of 3.34 suggests that, on average, respondents' social skills development is highly observable within the school success. This suggests that the significance of social skills in contributing to students' overall success in school. Social skills such as communication, cooperation, empathy, and conflict resolution play a vital role in academic achievement, classroom participation, and building positive relationships with teachers and peers.

In line with this, the indicator, **as a student, I respect the opinions and perspectives of others, even if they differ from my own**, got the highest mean of **3.57**, described as **highly observable** and interpreted as **very high**. This suggests that students are demonstrating an open-minded and inclusive attitude towards diverse perspectives. This is crucial for creating a positive and respectful school climate where students feel valued and accepted regardless of their beliefs or backgrounds. It implies a school culture

that prioritizes empathy, open-mindedness, and respectful communication among students. This culture extends beyond academic achievement to encompass the development of essential social skills necessary for success in diverse personal, academic, and professional contexts. Additionally, it suggests that educators and administrators are fostering an environment where students feel empowered to express their opinions and engage in meaningful dialogue, contributing to a rich and intellectually stimulating learning environment.

Davis (2022) explores the concept of empathy and its role in interpersonal relationships. The study discusses how perspective-taking abilities contribute to understanding and respecting the perspectives of others, even when they differ from one's own. It emphasizes the importance of empathy in fostering positive social interactions and reducing conflict. He emphasizes how empathy facilitates the recognition and validation of differing perspectives, even when they diverge from one's own. Through perspective-taking, individuals acknowledge the validity of others' viewpoints and demonstrate respect for their unique experiences and beliefs. This understanding fosters positive social interactions characterized by mutual respect, empathy, and acceptance of diversity.

On the other hand, the indicator, **as a student, I am able to adapt to different social situations and environments within the school community**, got the lowest mean of **3.13**, described as **observable** and interpreted as **high**. A low mean for this indicator may indicate that some students struggle to adapt to diverse social situations, potentially leading to feelings of isolation or exclusion. Schools may need to implement strategies to promote inclusivity and help students feel more comfortable navigating different social contexts. The findings suggest a need for targeted interventions aimed at improving students' adaptive social skills. These interventions could include social skills training programs, peer mentoring initiatives, or counseling services designed to support students in developing the confidence and resilience needed to navigate various social contexts successfully.

According to Elias and Haynes (2020), the study explores the relationship between social competence and academic achievement in elementary school children from minority, low-income, urban backgrounds. It emphasizes the importance of social skills development in schools, including the ability to adapt to various social situations, as a predictor of academic success and positive socio-emotional outcomes. Children who possess strong social competence skills are better able to navigate diverse social environments, interact effectively with peers and adults, and handle challenging social situations with confidence and resilience. Adaptability in social situations enables children to build positive relationships, resolve conflicts constructively, and collaborate productively, all of which contribute to their academic achievement and socio-emotional well-being.

Table 10. *Distribution of Respondents' Social Skills Development in terms of Peer Influence*

Indicators	Mean	Description
As a student, I agree that studying with academically motivated peers enhances my own academic achievement.	3.47	Highly Observable
As a student, I believe that peer encouragement to participate in educational activities improves academic outcomes.	3.43	Highly Observable
As a student, I feel confident in my academic abilities because of my peers' encouragement.	3.40	Highly Observable
Peer tutoring helps me improve my academic skills.	3.40	Highly Observable
Peer discussions about academic topics challenge my thinking and understanding.	3.37	Highly Observable
Overall	3.41	Highly Observable

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Highly Observable/Very High 1.76-2.50 Somewhat Observable/Low
 2.51-3.25 Observable/High 1.00-1.75 Not Observable/Very Low

Table 10 explains the distribution of respondents' social skills development in terms of peer influence with the overall mean of **3.41**, described as **highly observable** and interpreted as **very high**. This suggests that, on average, students exhibit socially adept behaviors influenced by their peers. Positive peer dynamics can foster a supportive social environment, where students learn from one another, collaborate effectively, and develop essential interpersonal skills. Peer influence significantly shapes students' social behaviors, attitudes, and norms. Schools need to recognize the power of peer culture in influencing students' social development and create strategies to promote positive peer interactions and norms.

In line with this, the indicator, **as a student, I agree that studying with academically motivated peers enhances my own academic achievement**, got the highest mean of **3.47**, described as **highly observable** and interpreted as **very high**. It implies that fostering a peer environment where students are academically motivated can substantially enhance overall academic achievement within the school community. This recognition highlights the importance of peer influence in shaping academic attitudes and behaviors among students. Moreover, it suggests that promoting collaborative learning experiences and peer support networks can be effective strategies for improving academic outcomes and creating a culture of excellence within the school. Additionally, the high mean for this indicator underscores the value students place on learning from and being surrounded by peers who are driven to succeed academically, indicating a desire for environments that support and encourage academic growth and achievement.

According to Sacerdote (2021), the study provides valuable insights into the influence of peer effects on academic achievement, particularly in the context of college roommates. By analyzing a dataset of randomly assigned college roommates at Dartmouth College, the study offers empirical evidence of the positive impact of academically motivated peers on students' academic performance. It implies that exposure to academically motivated peers may motivate individuals to exert greater effort and engagement in their academic pursuits. Observing the diligence and success of roommates who prioritize their studies may inspire students to emulate similar behaviors, leading to enhanced academic performance. This highlights the importance of peer influence in shaping students' attitudes, behaviors, and academic outcomes.

On the other hand, the indicator, **peer discussions about academic topics challenge my thinking and understanding**, got the lowest mean of **3.37**, described as **highly observable** and interpreted as **very high**. It implies that while peer discussions about academic topics are frequently observed within the school community, there may be a discrepancy between their visibility and their perceived impact on students' thinking and understanding. Despite their high observability, the low mean suggests that students may not fully recognize or appreciate the cognitive challenges posed by these discussions. This indicates a potential missed opportunity for leveraging peer interactions to stimulate critical thinking, deepen understanding, and enhance academic growth. Furthermore, it suggests a need for educators to actively facilitate and scaffold peer discussions to ensure that they effectively challenge students' thinking and promote meaningful learning experiences.

According to Hadwin et al. (2021), they discuss the concept of socially shared regulation of learning, wherein learners collaborate with peers to regulate their cognitive and metacognitive processes. Peer discussions play a key role in co-regulating learning, as students negotiate meaning, monitor comprehension, and provide feedback to each other. Through collaborative regulation, students challenge and scaffold each other's thinking, leading to deeper understanding and improved academic performance.

Research Question 4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of 2nd year BEED parental involvement and their social skills development in terms of:

- 4.1. educational environment;**
- 4.2. school success; and**
- 4.3. peer influence**

Table 11. *Test of Relationship between Parental Involvement and their Social Skills Development*

Parental Involvement	SOCIAL SKILLS DEVELOPMENT								
	Educational Environment			School Success			Peer Influence		
	r-value	p-value	Significance	r-value	p-value	Significance	r-value	p-value	Significance
Social Interaction	0.090	0.0023*	S	0.475	0.0236*	S	0.890	0.0423*	S
Learning Experience	0.490	0.0521	NS	0.890	0.0785	NS	0.568	0.0568	NS
Decision-making	0.900	0.0321*	S	0.567	0.0743	NS	0.929	0.0683	NS
Overall	0.740	0.0288*	S	0.644	0.0588	NS	0.7957	0.0558	NS

Table 11 shows the correlation coefficients (r-values) and p-values of the relationship between parental involvement and their level of social skills development in terms of educational environment, school success, and peer influence. The test was utilized to investigate whether a statistically significant relationship existed between parental involvement and their level of social skills development.

The data illustrate the significant relationship in the parental involvement in terms of social interaction across educational environment, school success, and peer influence and decision-making across educational environment. When considering the respondents' social interaction, the analysis reveals a statistically significant relationship in all three dimension of social skills development based on educational environment (r-value = 0.090 and p-value = 0.00273*), school success (r-value = 0.475 and p-value = 0.0236*), and peer influence (r-value = 0.893 and p-value = 0.0423*). There is also a statistically significant relationship on the respondents' decision-making in educational environment (r-value = 0.900 and p-value = 0.0321*).

Similarly, for learning experience, the correlation coefficient with educational environment, school success, and peer influence, and for decision-making, the correlation coefficient with school success, and peer influence are not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). The lack of significance suggests that there is no substantial relationship between parental involvement and social skills development in the learning experience. There is also no substantial relationship between social skills development and parental involvement in decision-making in school success and peer influence.

In conclusion, the data from table 11 do support the presence of a significant relationship between parental Involvement and their level of social skills development

particularly in terms of social interaction across various dimensions such as educational environment, school success, and peer influence. The statistically significant correlation coefficients (r-values) and p-values indicate that higher levels of parental involvement are associated with enhanced social skills development in these areas.

Research Question 5. Is there a significant difference in the respondents' level of assessment of the 2nd year BEED parental involvement and their social skills development when grouped according to:

- 5.1. age;**
- 5.2. gender;**
- 5.3. parents' occupation; and**
- 5.4. economic status**

Table 12. *Test of Difference between Parental Involvement and the level of Social Skills Development when grouped according to Characteristics*

Characteristics	Parental Involvement			Social Skills Development		
	r-value	p-value	Significance	r-value	p-value	Significance
Age	0.980	0.0567	NS	0.173	0.7348	NS
Gender	0.906	0.7980	NS	0.795	0.0590	NS
Parents' Occupation	0.985	0.0453*	S	0.194	0.0001*	S
Economic Status	0.905	0.0286*	S	0.109	0.0143*	S
Overall	0.944	0.2944	NS	0.3178	0.2021	NS

Table 12 depicts the differences between the respondents' assessment of parental involvement and social skills development. The data revealed that the respondents' parents' occupation and economic status have significant correlations with either the parental involvement or social skills development. This implies that factors such as parents' occupation and economic status do strongly influence the perceptions of parental involvement and social skills development.

On the other hand, a notable finding is the not significant correlation observed in the assessment of parental involvement and social skills development. This implies that factors such as age and gender do not strongly influence of the perceptions of parental involvement and social skills development.

As a whole, the lack of significant correlation between the assessment of parental involvement and social skills development suggests that individual differences, such as age and gender, may not be as influential in shaping perceptions of parental involvement and social skills development among respondents. This finding implies that regardless of

demographic characteristics like age or gender, individuals may perceive parental involvement and social skills development similarly.

However, the significant correlations found with parents' occupation and economic status highlight the importance of socio-economic factors in shaping these perceptions. It indicates that individuals from different socio-economic backgrounds may have varying perspectives on parental involvement and its impact on social skills development. For instance, those from higher socio-economic backgrounds might perceive greater levels of parental involvement and attribute it to enhanced social skills development, while individuals from lower socio-economic backgrounds might have different perceptions due to varying levels of access to resources and support systems.

Research Question 6. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan on parental involvement and social skills development can be designed?

Rationale

Understanding the factors that influence social skills development in children is crucial for promoting their overall well-being and future success. One key factor is parental involvement. This study aims to explore the relationship between parental involvement and children's social skills development, based on the premise that active and engaged parenting can significantly enhance a child's social competencies. It involves the relationship between parental involvement and social skills development.

The respondents' perception of parental involvement and social skills development learning experience is rated highest. Peer influence ranked the highest, which implies that social skills development is high quality.

The study determined a significant relationship between parental involvement and the social skills development in terms of social interaction, learning experience, and decision-making, but it found no significant relationship in learning experience.

Furthermore, the study identified a significant difference between the level of parental involvement and the level of social skills development when grouped according to characteristics. Regarding the respondents' characteristics, significant correlations were observed in the parents' occupation and economic status with the assessment of parental involvement and social skills development.

General Objectives

From the findings of the study, an action plan was formulated with the following objectives:

1. Clearer understanding of the factors that mediate the relationship between parental involvement and learning experiences and why this does not significantly impact social skills development;

2. Identify whether there are significant differences in parental involvement and social skills development levels based on respondents' characteristics such as age, gender, parents' occupation, and economic status;
3. Based on the study findings, develop actionable recommendation that can help parents effectively support their children's social skills development; and
4. Determine how different forms of parental involvement impact children's social interaction skills.

Table 13. Matrix of Action Plan

Areas of concern	Specific Objectives	Strategies/ Activities	Time Frame	Person/s Involved	Estimated Budget	Expected Outcomes
Parent and Community Engagement	To increase parental involvement in school activities and decision-making processes.	Monthly parent-teacher conferences, quarterly workshops on topics such as supporting literacy at home or understanding the curriculum.	Throughout the academic year	Teachers, school administrators, parent-teacher association (PTA) members.	1,500	Improved communication between parents and teachers, increased parental understanding of school initiatives and their child's educational needs.
Parental Involvement and Support	To provide resources and support for parents to enhance their involvement in their children's education.	Offer workshops, seminars, and informational sessions on topics such as effective parenting strategies, understanding the curriculum, and supporting homework.	Throughout the academic year	Teachers, students, parent coordinators, school counselors, community partners.	2,000	Increased parental confidence in supporting their children's education, enhanced parent-child communication, and improved academic outcomes for students.

Peer Leadership and Mentorship	To foster peer leadership skills through leadership development opportunities and experiences	Offer leadership training workshops, seminars, or retreats for selected students interested in serving as peer leaders.	Beginning of the school year	School administrators, teachers, leadership coaches, older student mentors	1,500	Increased confidence and competence in leadership abilities among students, enhanced peer relationships and collaboration, and a positive impact on the school culture.
Friendship and Peer Relationships	To foster open communication and trust between you and your parents regarding peer relationships.	Create a supportive and non-judgmental environment where you feel comfortable discussing peer-related issues with your parents.	Beginning of the school year	Parents, counselor, teachers	1,000	Strengthened parent-child relationship, increased trust and support from parents in navigating peer relationships, and enhanced emotional well-being.
Timeliness of Feedback	To solicit feedback from students and parents regarding the effectiveness of the feedback process.	Administer surveys to students and parents at regular intervals to assess satisfaction with the feedback process and gather suggestions for improvement.	Beginning of the school year	School administrators, teachers, parents, students.	500	Insight into the effectiveness of the feedback process, identification of areas for improvement, and enhanced satisfaction and engagement among students and parents.

Critical Thinking	To enhance students' ability to evaluate the advantages and disadvantages of different options through critical thinking.	Integrate critical thinking exercises and discussions into the curriculum across various subjects and topics.	Beginning of the school year	Teachers, curriculum developers, educational specialists	500	Improved analytical skills, deeper understanding of complex issues, and the ability to make well-informed decisions.
Classroom Environment	To provide opportunities for students to engage in creative expression and innovation through project-based learning and hands-on activities.	Assign open-ended projects that allow students to choose topics of personal interest, collaborate with peers, and present their findings in creative formats such as multimedia presentations, art installations, or performances.	Throughout the academic year	Teachers, students	500	Increased student motivation, engagement, and ownership of learning outcomes, as well as enhanced creativity and problem-solving skills.
Social Skills Development	To develop active listening skills to understand and respond empathetically to others' perspectives and experiences.	Facilitate activities that promote active listening, such as pair-share discussions, group reflections, and empathy-building exercises.	Throughout the academic year	Teachers, school counselors, peer mentors	500	Enhanced listening skills, increased empathy and understanding of diverse perspectives, and stronger interpersonal connections.
Engagement and Participation	To ensure that all students actively	Use techniques like think-pair-share,	Beginning of the	Teachers, instructional coaches,	800	Increased engagement and participation

	engage in peer discussions and contribute their perspectives and insights.	where students first reflect individually, then discuss in pairs before sharing with the whole group.	school year	student leaders.		among all students, leading to a more dynamic and inclusive learning environment.
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Discussion

Parental involvement plays a critical role in the development of a child's social skills. When parents actively engage in their children's lives, whether through open communication, collaborative problem-solving, or shared activities, they create an environment that fosters emotional intelligence and interpersonal skills. For instance, children who observe and experience positive interactions within the family are more likely to replicate these behaviors in social settings. Parents can further support social development by encouraging participation in group activities, modeling effective conflict resolution, and teaching empathy through discussions about others' feelings and perspectives. Additionally, a strong parent-child bond provides children with the confidence to navigate complex social situations, as they feel secure in the support and guidance of their caregivers. In essence, consistent and thoughtful parental involvement not only strengthens familial relationships but also equips children with the social tools necessary for lifelong success.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers arrived at these conclusions:

The study "Parental Involvement and Social Skills Development of Selected 2nd Year BEED Students at St. Peter's College: Basis for Academic Support" has revealed significant insights into the impact of parental involvement on the social skills development of students. The data collected through face-to-face surveys from 30 selected second-year BEED students highlighted that active parental engagement, particularly in social interactions and learning experiences is crucial in enhancing students' social skills. The significant correlation found between parental involvement and various aspects of social skills development underscores the importance of parents actively participating in their children's educational and social activities.

The analysis of the demographic data indicated that most respondents were females aged 19 to 21, with parents predominantly engaged in self-employment. The study found that parental involvement in learning experiences had the highest impact on students, followed closely by social interaction, while decision-making had a lesser but notable effect. In terms of social skills development, peer influence emerged as the most

significantly impacted area, followed by school success and the educational environment. These findings suggest that different aspects of parental involvement contribute variably to the development of specific social skills, emphasizing the multifaceted nature of parental roles in education.

In conclusion, the study highlighted that parental involvement is crucial for the students' social and academic success. Active participation from parents, particularly in social interactions and learning experiences, significantly correlates with improved social skills among students. The findings advocate for enhanced parental engagement programs and support systems within educational institutions to foster better student outcomes. Future research should continue to explore these dynamics across diverse populations and settings to further validate and expand upon these findings.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion drawn from the study, the following recommendations are provided:

1. Students should regularly share their academic and social experiences with their parents to foster better understanding and support. Open communication can help address challenges more effectively.
2. Parents should strive to be more involved in their children's education by attending school events, parent-teacher meetings, and participating in school activities.
3. Teachers should actively encourage and facilitate parental participation in school activities and student learning processes.
4. School administrators should implement and promote programs that encourage greater parental involvement in school activities and decision-making processes.
5. Future researchers should conduct studies involving diverse demographic groups to understand how different cultural and socio-economic backgrounds affect parental involvement and social skills development.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ensuring the privacy and anonymity of students participating in the research was paramount to encourage honest and open responses. Several ethical concerns were addressed to uphold these principles. First, informed consent was obtained from all participating students, with a clear explanation of the study's purpose, the data collection process, and how their information would be used. This also ensured that participants could withdraw from the study at any time without consequences. Second, data de-identification was implemented by removing or replacing personally identifiable information, such as names, school names, or contact details, during analysis. Pseudonyms were assigned to participants to further protect their identities. Third, secure data storage measures were adopted, such as storing data securely with encryption and limiting access to authorized personnel, to prevent accidental disclosure to unauthorized parties. Finally, ethical approval was obtained from an institutional review board (IRB) or ethics committee to ensure that the research design and data handling procedures

adhered to established ethical standards. These measures collectively safeguarded the rights and confidentiality of all participants.

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